

THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT METHODS

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Abstract: *The widespread introduction of digitalization in all spheres of modern life is becoming an objective reality. The application of digitalization at the enterprise changes both the external environment of the organization in terms of the conditions of interaction with the state, suppliers and buyers, and the internal processes taking place in the company, in particular, in the field of management. In modern conditions, organizations should look at their own business taking into account the approaches of the digital economy.*

Conventionally, a "non-digital" organization, whose work is based on outdated principles, is somehow forced to adapt to new conditions or leave the market, giving way to new enterprises and companies following modern trends. Like it or not, the costs of research, development, consulting services and employee training will inevitably increase as part of the digitalization of the company. Companies that are not ready for such a development will sooner or later leave the market. On the other hand, digitalization should not become an end in itself. It is necessary to calculate the effectiveness of certain changes in order to confidently assert that the key processes at the enterprise will significantly improve as a result of the introduction of digital technologies. Companies that have already switched to digital rails are faced with the fact that approaches to managing an organization need to be changed taking into account the features of the new digital reality.

The tasks of managing an organization in the conditions of digitalization include the following:

- changing the company's business processes based on advanced digital technologies;
- maintaining a high level of knowledge of company management and specialists in the field of modern technologies;
- maintaining a high degree of readiness for changes and challenges of the external environment.

When introduced into the company's activities, digital technologies provide a number of advantages, among which it is possible to highlight the increase in production flexibility by proactively changing the

characteristics of the production process and ensuring information integration of the stages of the life cycle of manufactured products. Digital transformation provides a qualitative improvement of the business processes of the enterprise through the introduction of innovations and the adaptation of business models to the conditions of the modern digital economy.

The banking sector and financial services, IT and software development, as well as industrial production can be identified as industry leaders in the process of implementing a digital transformation strategy. The industries in which digitalization is developing the worst are the business services (maintenance and support), the entertainment industry and construction. According to expert estimates, among the factors hindering digital transformation, the following can be indicated: lack of a structured strategy, shortage of qualified personnel, low level of competence and knowledge among employees of enterprises, lack of integration of new and existing technologies and data, inflexible or slow processes, outdated technologies, lack of close ties between IT and business, unwillingness to change, insufficient funding, management's position, possible risks.

In modern conditions of digitalization, industrial enterprises have to reorganize their activities, including in connection with the introduction of information systems. This is associated with serious risks, since the implementation of ready-made or custom-designed projects often ends in failure. Existing methods and tools do not always allow to reduce risks and solve issues of reorganization of business processes of the enterprise at various stages. The methodology of building a complex system of enterprise activities is of great importance. Developing an effective approach to managing business processes and new technologies in an enterprise is not an easy task. In order to ensure the sustainable development of an industrial enterprise, it is required to apply innovative management theories and methodologies. The processes taking place at the enterprise require constant attention from the management, process owners and employees who ensure the implementation of business processes. In the process of improving and optimizing processes, it is necessary to maintain the level of efficiency and the successes achieved as a result of the implementation of the process approach.

To implement the process of digital transformation of an enterprise, the following algorithm can be used:

1. formation of a competent expert working group capable of conducting diagnostics of the organization's activities and ongoing business processes;
2. conducting self-examination of the company's activities and forming

an array of initial data on the level of digitalization of the enterprise and production business processes, on the software components of digital production used;

3. assessment of the level of digitalization (digital maturity) and the level of information security of the enterprise;

4. identification of bottlenecks, identification of priority areas for the introduction of digital technologies, risk assessment;

5. analysis of existing or development of new concepts of digitalization of the enterprise in the chosen priority direction;

6. formation of a roadmap for the introduction of digital technologies;

7. decision-making at the level of the head of the organization on the economic feasibility, effectiveness of the use and implementation of digital technologies in the activities of the enterprise, approval of the implementation roadmap;

8. implementation of the roadmap for the introduction of digital technologies;

9. control and analysis of the results of implementation and key performance indicators of the enterprise in order to make adjustments;

10. in the presence of positive dynamics, the study of scaling issues

Thus, it can be noted that the decision to use modern technologies in management will affect the activities of the entire enterprise and it is necessary to take into account the risks associated with this. Obtaining the desired effect is possible only with careful planning and comprehensive study of promising technologies, their positive and negative sides, and it is also necessary to take into account the peculiarities of enterprise management in the conditions of digitalization. Building flexible organizational structures is possible with the use of digital information technologies.

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